

THE MECHANISM OF GALVANIC BLISTERING IN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon/polymer composites form blisters when galvanically coupled to steel or aluminum in sea water or sodium chloride solution. Chemical analyses of blister fluids were conducted. The mechanism of galvanic blistering is proposed. According to this mechanism, galvanic coupling produces a surface charge on the fibers which results in modification of the polymer/fiber bonding. This makes possible a water clustering at the interface which starts the delamination process. Oxygen reduction takes place at these zones producing hydroxyl ions and a sodium hydroxide solution is formed. The sodium hydroxide solution creates an osmotic pressure which causes the blister to grow.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon reinforced polymer composites find excellent use in such structural applications where high performance and light weight are desired. Some examples are aerospace structures, marine off-shore structures, automotive body panels, sports racquets, etc. Carbon is an electrically conductive material and also a noble cathode material. Therefore, engineering metals like steel and aluminum undergo rapid corrosion when galvanically coupled to carbon in aqueous electrolyte environment like seawater or salt water¹. When carbon fibers of a carbon/polymer composite are subjected to such galvanic conditions, the composite forms blisters containing liquids of pH 14. Carbon reinforced vinyl ester composites were studied in the current research. Samples of carbon composite with vinyl ester matrix exposed to both seawater and NaCl solution under non-galvanic conditions did not show blisters (which implies that the vinyl ester used is highly resistant to hydrolysis) whereas galvanically coupled samples form blisters within two weeks. The blistering of carbon fiber composites under galvanic conditions is termed 'galvanic or electrochemical blistering'. Galvanic blistering of carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester was first reported by Tucker². Other carbon reinforced composites which also blister under galvanic conditions are carbon reinforced polyester³, epoxy⁴ and polyamide⁵ composites. Galvanic blisters in these composites were also filled with liquids of pH 14. Therefore, galvanic blistering appears to be a general phenomenon in carbon fiber composites with various polymeric matrices.

Microscopy studies revealed blister opening in carbon/vinyl ester composites to be along the carbon/fiber and matrix interface³. However, the effects of galvanic coupling on the mechanical properties of the carbon composites are not well established although evidence for 30% reduction in shear strength in carbon-epoxy composites, subjected to galvanic conditions, has been presented by Sloan⁵. But very little or no studies exist concerning the underlying mechanisms which lead to galvanic blistering in carbon/polymer composites. The objective of the current research was to

determine the mechanism of galvanic blistering in carbon/vinyl ester composites.

The cathodic reaction on carbon surfaces in neutral or basic solutions is the electrochemical reduction of oxygen,

with equilibrium potentials around 0.2 Volts (V) against standard calomel electrode. This is well established. The potential versus current density profiles (Tafel plots) for the carbon/vinyl ester composite² and the high pH of the blister fluids indicate that the cathodic reaction at the carbon/polymer interface is the oxygen reduction reaction (equation (1)).

Sloan et al⁶ observed dissolution of epoxy matrix in the carbon/epoxy composites subjected to galvanic coupling with magnesium anodes in seawater. These researchers hypothesized that an intermediate step in the reaction (1) is the production of perhydroxyl ions, HO_2^- which might have attacked the epoxy polymer as the perhydroxyls are several times more reactive than hydroxyl ions. However no experimental evidence exists in support of the above mechanism. Donnellan et al observed the dissolution of polyamides in galvanically coupled carbon-polyamide composites⁵. However, no visual attack of the vinyl ester was observed when a piece of cast vinyl ester was exposed to pH 14 sodium hydroxide solution for two weeks.

A critical step in the investigation of galvanic blistering mechanisms is the chemical analysis of the blister fluids. Blister fluid analysis was conducted using several analytical techniques which gave different complementary information. Morphological studies of dried products of blister fluid were also conducted using optical and electron microscopy. The mechanism of galvanic blistering is proposed based on the results from these studies.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Materials Studied

The following were the materials studied:

(a) A commercial composite containing unidirectional T 300 carbon fiber mats with glass wefts in cross-weave, laid up in a Derakane 470-36 vinyl ester resin matrix. Details of curing conditions are unknown for this composite except that the curing of the polymer in this composite was initiated by methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) (b) T 300 carbon fibers/Derakane 470-36 vinyl ester resin matrix. This composite was cured at room temperature using MEKP as initiator and cobalt naphthanate (CoNap) as accelerator. (c) Cast vinyl ester on solid graphite disk samples. (d) Cast vinyl ester on 0.5 mm thick rectangular shaped silver substrates. The curing procedure for materials (c) and (d) were identical as for the material (b). The vinyl ester coated graphite disk and silver samples were intended to check galvanic blistering in the absence of surface treatments which were used on T 300 carbon fibers.

2.2. Galvanic Conditions

The samples of the materials described in section (2.1) were connected to 1" x 0.25" x 0.125" (25mm x 6.25mm x 3.13mm) low carbon steel pieces (anodes in the galvanic couple) and were submerged in 3%(by weight) sodium chloride solution. These samples were left exposed to galvanic conditions at room temperature until blisters grew to sufficient size to extract adequate amounts of blister fluids.

2.3. Blister Fluid Sampling

The blister fluid collection was a difficult task since the blisters were small in size usually of 5mm maximum diameter. The blisters formed on carbon fiber/vinyl ester composite samples were usually oval shaped with the maximum and minimum dimensions of 5mm and 2 mm respectively. Liquids were collected from the blisters using disposable 0.25 and 0.5 μl (mm^3) glass capillaries. The liquid yield per blister was as low as 0.5 μl (mm^3). The liquids were deposited on to the characteristic sample holders of different analytical instruments and were allowed to dry or diluted depending on the analytical method.

2.4. Analytical Methods

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) of the blister fluid dried products was performed. A Perkin-Elmer 1600 series FTIR instrument was used. The sample holders used were CaF₂ crystals. This technique yields information on the chemical bonds in the sample, e.g., C=C, C-C, C-O, O-H bonds.

Size Exclusion/High Performance Liquid Chromatography (SEC/HPLC) was employed to determine the number of components and their corresponding molecular weights. A Waters 501 HPLC pump and a Waters 746 Datamodule were used to pump the solvent and store the data respectively. A Waters R401 differential refractometer was used to detect the components of the samples. The solvent used was deionized, distilled water. A Ultrahydrogel™ 120 gel permeation column was used for component separation. The column is packed with polymethylmethacrylate gel and is compatible with aqueous based samples. The column can separate molecular weights in the range 100 to 2000 g/gmol. The column was calibrated using polyethylene glycol standards. All runs were performed at a stable room temperature of 21°C. The sample injection size was 10μl (mm³). Blister fluids were diluted 10 times to arrive at the required sample size for the HPLC.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) study was conducted to understand the morphology of the products which condensed from the blister fluid. *Energy Dispersive Analysis by X-rays (EDAX)* was conducted to obtain the elemental composition of the components of blister fluid. *Electron Diffraction* was also performed for various samples.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was imperative to identify the species which are *necessary* to galvanic blistering phenomenon. The possible sources of species from which blister fluids can form are (a) electrochemical species produced at the carbon surface, (b) the carbon fiber material, (c) surface treatments on the fibers, (d) the polymer and (e) electrolyte and other species dissolved in the polymer. The analytical results showed which of the above species are necessary for galvanic blistering.

Both the vinyl ester coated silver and graphite disk samples coupled to steel in 3% NaCl solution formed blisters within two weeks. These blisters contain pH 14 liquids. Carbon and silver in the galvanic couples considered act as electrocatalysts for the reduction of oxygen to hydroxyl ions and besides their electrochemical oxidation potentials are much greater than the potentials they are subjected to in these couples. Therefore carbon fiber composite and polymer coated silver support identical electrochemical reactions in the galvanic couples with steel in 3% NaCl solution. The comparison of results of blister fluid chemical analysis for these two systems would reveal several important mechanistic aspects of galvanic blistering.

3.1. Analytical Results

FTIR Results: The FTIR spectra obtained for the blister fluids from carbon fiber/vinyl ester sample, vinyl ester coated silver and graphite disk samples are shown in Figure (1). All the spectra are identical implying that the blister fluids from the three samples have identical compositions. This is a significant result which says that the blistering phenomenon is same for these three cathodes. The huge absorption peak at about 3500 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the hydrogen bonding of water. The conclusion is that the blister fluids are aqueous solutions. The absorptions at about 2200 cm⁻¹ and the and 1600 cm⁻¹ are characteristic absorptions of O-H bonds of hydroxyl ions. The absorption peak at 2400 cm⁻¹ is from CO₂ absorption from the background. The only characteristic peak for the blister fluids is the 1390 cm⁻¹. The huge O-H absorption bands between 1500 and 2000 cm⁻¹ might mask any absorption peaks of C=C, C-C, etc. of a polymer which occur in this range. Therefore the FTIR spectrum of dried blister fluid products are shown in Figure (2). The spectra reveal no absorptions in the wavenumber range of 1500-2000 cm⁻¹ characteristic of any C=C, C-C, C-O or C-H bonds in a polymer. It can be concluded that the blister fluid products did not contain polymer breakdown species. The only peak common to both the spectra is the one at 1425 cm⁻¹ which is the absorption by the same species that gives an

absorption at 1390 cm^{-1} when in solution as shown in Figure (1). Thus, the FTIR spectra reveal that there is some common species in the blister fluid solutions from all the samples. The spectra also show no evidence of any polymer species in the solution. The absorption peak at about 1600 cm^{-1} for the carbon composite sample corresponds to O-H bonds of water molecules in Figure (2). Why this peak is present even though the blister fluid is dried will be clearer in the subsequent part of the discussion.

SEC/HPLC Results: The plot in Figure (3) shows elution data corresponding to peaks recorded for the test and calibration samples. The molecular separation region is between 100 and 2000 g/gmol as indicated by the calibration curve. The elution volume of 6.8 ml for a sample of extract of vinyl ester resin in water corresponds to a molecular weight of 1500. It indicates that there is some solubility of vinyl ester monomer in water. However, no peak was detected in this range for the sample run of blister fluid indicating that no vinyl ester molecules were present in the blister fluid solution. The one peak detected at the elution volume of 12 ml for the blister fluid sample must correspond to a strong ionic species present in the solution because strongly ionic species get retarded in the column and elute late. This is consistent with the high pH nature of the blister fluid solution. An important conclusion from HPLC analysis is that there is no high molecular weight species present in the blister fluid, the result which is consistent with the absence of any polymer bond absorption peaks in the FTIR spectra of Figure (2). This is further evidence that polymer was not attacked during the blistering process.

TEM/ED/EDAX Results: The TEM micrographs of blister fluid dried products from the carbon composite and silver composite are shown in Figures (4) and (5) respectively. The gel like substance shown by two arrows in Figure (4) is an amorphous substance as they did not show any electron diffraction pattern. The EDAX elemental analysis spectrum for this is shown in Figure (6). The Cu and C peaks are from the specimen carbon coated copper grid. The Cr peak is from the specimen holder in the equipment. The characteristic peaks from the amorphous substance are Na, O and Si. It was concluded that the substance must be sodium silicate or a water glass type of material. Silicon must come from the glass fibers having been attacked by the sodium hydroxide in the blister fluid. Sodium silicate is highly hygroscopic and that is the reason why even the dried blister fluid products from the carbon composite show some O-H absorption in the corresponding FTIR spectrum in Figure (2).

The particles shown by a single arrow in Figure (4) are crystalline substances which showed strong electron diffraction pattern. The particles in the dried blister fluid solutions from the silver sample in Figure (5) also are found to be crystalline from electron diffraction study. The EDAX spectrum for the elemental analysis of the crystals in Figure (5) is shown in Figure (7). The Cu and Cr peaks were from the Cu grid on which the sample was collected and from the specimen holder respectively. The elements in the crystals therefore are C, O and Na. Since no polymer C-O peaks were found in the FTIR spectrum in Figure (2), the crystals could be of inorganic nature. Sodium carbonate crystals were suspected. The FTIR spectrum of sodium carbonate solution is shown in Figure (8). The spectrum is identical to those of the blister fluid solution in Figure (1). The spectrum shows the characteristic peak of C-O bond of the carbonate ion at 1390 cm^{-1} . Since the FTIR spectra are identical for the blister fluids from all the samples, the crystals shown by the single arrow in Figure (4) for the dried blister fluid products from carbon composite sample must also be sodium carbonate crystals.

What is the source of sodium carbonate? The dissolved atmospheric carbon dioxide in the NaCl solution in the form of H^+HCO_3^- (carbonic acid) will be neutralized by the NaOH solution in the blister fluid forming sodium carbonate. This was confirmed by the following experiment. A silver cathode is subjected to a cathodic potential of -900 mV in a 3% NaCl solution. The electrolyte near the silver cathode was restrained by covering the electrode with a polyethylene bag. This retards the diffusion of sodium carbonate away from the electrode. The concentration of sodium carbonate in the restrained electrolyte rises as a result. The FTIR spectrum obtained for this restrained electrolyte is compared with the FTIR spectrum of the blister fluid from the vinyl ester coated silver cathode in Figure (9). In fact the restrained electrolyte shows absorption at about 1390 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of sodium carbonate.

Thus, the galvanic blister fluids are essentially aqueous solutions of sodium hydroxide and sodium carbonate. In the case of carbon fiber composites, sodium silicate is also present which was due to attack of the glass fibers by the sodium hydroxide solution. The polymer is not

chemically involved in galvanic blistering except that it acts as a permeable membrane to the electrolyte and also as a barrier for the diffusion of the species generated at the cathode.

3.2. The Galvanic Blistering Mechanism

Based on the knowledge of electrochemical reaction at the carbon cathode surface and the analytical results of the blister fluids the following mechanism for galvanic blistering is proposed:

Nucleation of Blister. The carbon fibers are negatively charged (electron rich) as soon as the galvanic couple is established. The polymer layer adhering to the carbon fiber surface experiences an electric field due to the fiber charging. The electron dense regions of the polymer chains close to the carbon surface tend to move away from the negatively charged carbon surface. This will result in some adhesive bonds being broken. Due to zero partial pressure of water in the debonded regions, water molecules in the surrounding electrolyte-saturated-polymer diffuse into these regions and a layer of water molecules condensed as an aqueous film is created.

Blister Growth. The sodium ions and dissolved oxygen molecules in the surrounding polymer can now dissolve in water created in the debonded regions. The adsorption of oxygen on to the debonded carbon surface sets up the oxygen reduction reaction which results in the production of hydroxyl ions. The hydroxyl ions are neutralized by more sodium ions entering the region. Thus, a sodium hydroxide solution is formed in the debonded regions. Sodium hydroxide being highly hygroscopic, draws more water into the region from the surroundings. The diffusion rate of sodium hydroxide ions through the polymer is less than the diffusion rate of water in the polymer. This sets up an osmotic pressure within the debonded region. The osmotic pressure will deform the polymer layer and will result in the increased debonding. The continuous production of sodium hydroxide as a result of the electrochemical reduction of oxygen at the cathode surface sustains the blister growth.

It follows from the above mechanism that the vinyl ester layer is not chemically involved in the blistering process but acts as the semipermeable membrane producing osmotic pressure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Carbon reinforced vinyl ester composite forms blisters when galvanically coupled to steel or aluminum in seawater or 3% NaCl solution. The blisters were filled with liquid of pH 14 and the blister opening is along the fiber/polymer interface. Polymer coated silver also produced similar blisters under identical conditions. Chemical analysis of the blister fluids was performed using FTIR, SEC/HPLC and TEM/EDAX techniques. The analysis results show that the blister fluids contain essentially aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide and sodium carbonate. The sodium hydroxide forms as a result of cathodic reduction of oxygen and the sodium carbonate is the result of neutralization of carbonic acid by sodium hydroxide. Dissolved carbon dioxide from the atmosphere exists as carbonic acid in the electrolyte.

The galvanic blistering mechanism is proposed based on the analytical results. Carbon fibers develop a surface charge when galvanically coupled. As a result, the electron dense parts of the adhering polymer chains repelled away from the carbon surface which will result in debonding. Water droplet nucleates in these debonded zones. This brings in sodium ions and oxygen into the region. Oxygen reduction to hydroxyls takes place on the carbon surface. As a result sodium hydroxide solution is formed. Sodium hydroxide is highly hygroscopic and draws more water into this region. The relatively greater diffusion rates of water through the polymer compared to sodium hydroxide solution builds an osmotic pressure in the debonded region. The blister grows under this pressure. The growth is sustained by continuous production of hydroxyl ions which maintains high concentration of sodium hydroxide in the blister liquid. The blister growth results in increased interface debonding with time.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support of this research by Dr. John Sedricks and the Office of Naval Research, United States of America under the grant # N00014911328.

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Figure 1. FTIR spectra of Galvanic Blister Fluids

X: Vinyl Ester Coated Silver; Y: Carbon/Glass/Vinyl Ester Composite;
Z: Vinyl Ester Coated Graphite Disk

Figure 2. FTIR spectra of Galvanic Blister Fluid Dried Products

X: Vinyl Ester Coated Silver; Y: Carbon/Glass/Vinyl Ester Composite;
Z: Vinyl Ester Coated Graphite Disk

Figure 3. SEC/HPLC Elution Data.

Figure 5. EDAX spectrum of Dried Blister Fluid Products from Carbon/Glass/Vinyl Ester Composite

Figure 4. TEM micrograph of Dried Blister Fluid Products from Carbon/Glass/Vinyl Ester Composite

Figure 6. TEM micrograph of Dried Blister Fluid Products from Vinyl Ester Coated Silver

Figure 7. EDAX spectrum of Dried Blister Fluid Products from Vinyl Ester Coated Silver

Figure 8. FTIR spectrum of Sodium Carbonate Solution

Figure 9. FTIR spectra of Restrained Electrolyte (X) and Blister Fluid from Vinyl Ester Coated Silver (Y)